

Toward a Standardized Robotics-Enabled Execution of Muscle Shortening Maneuver

Saad Jamshed Abbasi
Department of Information Engineering
University of Pisa, Italy
saadjamshed93@gmail.com

Piero Maria Orsini
Centro Piaggio
University of Pisa, Italy

Simone Rossi
Department of Information Engineering
University of Pisa, Italy
s.rossi85@studenti.unipi.it,

Riccardo Bracci
Centro Piaggio
University of Pisa, Italy
info @studiokinesiterapia.it

Matteo Bianchi
Centro Piaggio, Department of
information Engineering, Pisa University
matteo.bianchi@unipi.it

Paolo Lippi
Centro Piaggio
University of Pisa, Italy
ipaolo.lippi@gmail.com

Manuel G. Catalano
Soft Robotics for Human Rehabilitation
Italian Institute of Technology, Italy
manuel.catalano@iit.it

Abstract— The Muscle Shortening Maneuver (MSM) is a rehabilitation technique applicable to several pathological conditions. This approach involves passively elongating and shortening the targeted muscle group in the affected limb. Current rehabilitation centers implement these passive motions manually or through external actuators without feedback control, which can diminish the effectiveness and standardization of the MSM. In this research, we designed and developed a mechatronic device capable of accurately delivering the required motion to the upper limb. First, the motion parameters were extracted from therapy sessions conducted by experienced therapists at the rehabilitation clinic. Based on this information, the actuator was selected, and an experimental setup was developed. Sliding mode control with a sliding perturbation observer was implemented for precise motion control. Experiments were conducted on one healthy participant to validate the performance of the developed device. The results, although preliminary, suggest that our system is capable of producing oscillation within the desired motion range.

Keywords—Muscle shortening maneuver, Rehabilitation, Mechatronics, Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

The muscle-shortening maneuver (MSM) was introduced by Grimaldi in 1986 [1]. MSM is effective for treating various pathological conditions affecting different anatomical zones, among them the upper limb. During the procedure, the subject lies in a supine position with the upper limb raised. An added mass is applied to the limb, which is connected to a rope via springs. The therapist applies a series of rapid accelerations (either manually or with an open-loop actuator) to the limb through the rope. These external forces activate the muscle spindles, which in turn regulate muscle strength. Different studies had verified the effectiveness of MSM [2-4], for different pathological conditions and anatomical districts.

Recent clinical therapies induce fast acceleration manually and/or use open loop control (actuator). Studio Fisioterapico Lippi (Chiesina Uzzanese, Pistoia - Italy) used actuator to improve the standardization of therapy. However no feedback control was implemented and the therapist can regulate manually only the voltage of the motor. The system consists of supporting structure, set of pulleys to transfer motion, three phase induction motor (3PH Motor IEC 60034-30), and crank shaft mechanism attached to the motor to convert rotary motion into translational motion. The voltage controller is used to vary the frequency of applied motion. Similarly, therapist manually changes the length of crankshaft to

increase the amplitude of motion (Fig. 1). The limb is attached to the rope via three springs of same stiffness (stiffness of each spring is 500 N/m). These types of therapies are largely operator-dependent and not standardized and not standardized, hence experienced therapists are required to perform such maneuver. This can reduce the effectiveness and deployment of MSM.

To overcome these limitations, we designed and developed a mechatronic device to perform MSM in a more standardized way. The device uses a computer-controlled actuator to replicate the MSM. This actuator is integrated with MATLAB/Simulink, allowing the user to design a reference trajectory by specifying the amplitude and frequency of the signal. A robust control algorithm was implemented to track the reference signals. Experiments were conducted on healthy subjects (three trials) with the goal of tracking the reference trajectory with minimal tracking error. The results confirm that the device is effective in achieving the desired outcomes

II. DATA ACQUISITION AND MECHANICAL DESIGN

A. Data Acquisition

The mechanical architecture of the prototype is a replica of the current system used at Studio Fisioterapico Lippi. For this reason, our focus was on the actuation and control part. Experimental data were collected for selecting the actuator and designing the motion signal, including the frequency and amplitude of the applied motion. For data collection, footage of experiments performed with two healthy subjects was recorded on a mobile phone (duration of footage was 11 minutes for both subjects). The subjects were healthy and had no history of shoulder injuries. Their ages were 31 and 39 respectively. During the experiments, the subject lied in a supine position with the upper limb lifted upward, connected to a rope through set of three springs (same springs mentioned before). The other end of the rope was attached to the motor's crankshaft. The added mass of 3 kilogram (kg) was mounted at the upper arm of the limb. During the trials, the therapist applied different motions to the upper limb of the subjects. The main goal was to extract the amplitude, frequency, and velocity of the motion, with amplitude and frequency being particularly useful for designing the motion signal in our device. Kinova software was used to analyze these characteristics [5]. It provides information about the marked points in the footage. The range of the applied motion was between 2 and 6 cm, the frequency ranged from 0.8 to 1.2 Hz, and the velocity of the applied motion varied between 13.6 and 34.33 cm/s.

B. Mechanical Design

The CAD model was designed in Creo Parametric. It consists of two main structures: the support and the base. The structure is made from aluminum profiles (Fig. 1). An actuator is connected to the support structure through a flange. A 24-volt Maxon DC motor (RE 50: 568296) with a GP 62 A gearbox (110504) is used as the actuator. The nominal torque of the motor is 0.405 Nm, which is amplified 71 times by the gearbox. Similarly, the actuator rotational speed of 5,680 revolutions per minute (rpm) is reduced to 80 rpm (8.37758 rad/s) by the gearbox. The force required to lift the upper limb, with a safety factor, is assumed to be 200 N [6]. The goal is to convert the rotary motion of the actuator into translational motion at the other end. To achieve this, a disk needs to be mounted on the shaft of the gearbox. The radius of the disk should be chosen to provide the required speed and generate enough force to lift the upper limb. Therefore the radius of 9.5 cm was selected for the desired task. With the disk of 9.5 cm, the system can generate a velocity of 70 cm/s, and force of 302.6842 N. The before mentioned characteristics satisfy the requirement of the task.

III. CONTROL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Control

The goal of the control is to track a reference signal designed by the user on the basis of the experimental data collected in Sec. II A.. The system is nonlinear in nature, therefore robust control is required to achieve the objective of the study. Sliding mode control with sliding perturbation observer (SMCPSO) is implemented in MATLAB/ Simulink (Fig. 2) to track the reference trajectory [7].

B. Experimental Results

Experiments were conducted on a healthy 39-year-old subject to evaluate the prototype's performance, approved by the University of Pisa's Committee on Bioethics (Review No. 30/2020). The subject lay supine with the upper limb lifted. A variable reference trajectory was applied: no movement for the first 20 seconds, followed by increasing amplitude and frequency 2 cm at 0.85 Hz (21-80s), 3 cm at 0.9 Hz (81-140s), 4 cm at 1 Hz (141-200s), 5 cm at 1.1 Hz (201-260s), and 6 cm at 1.2 Hz (261-320s). A 3 kg weight was attached to the upper arm.

This section presents the tracking results of the controller. Control performance was evaluated using mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE). Data from three trials were processed, yielding an average MAE of 0.518716 cm (SD: 0.016051), with upper and lower limits of 0.531448 cm and 0.496075 cm, respectively. The average RMSE was 0.621539 cm (SD: 0.021162), with upper and lower limits of 0.638212 cm and 0.59168 cm, respectively. Trajectory tracking results for ten seconds are presented in Fig. 3. The duration of the experiment was 320 seconds, so it is not possible to present all the results.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The paper outlines the design and control of a mechatronic device for standardized MSM therapy, utilizing a computer-controlled actuator. Therapists can customize therapy parameters like amplitude and frequency via a computer. Preliminary trials with one healthy subject indicate the device's potential for standardization. Future research will

involve more subjects and the implementation of an admittance-based control algorithm to estimate limb stiffness.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by the European Union by the Next Generation EU Project ECS00000017 'Ecosistema dell'Innovazione' Tuscany Health Ecosystem (THE, PNRR, Spoke 9: Robotics and Automation for Health). *Piero Maria Orsini sadly passed away in January 2023. This article was written in his memory*

References

- [1] Grimaldi L, Lippi P, Marri P, Fantozzi M, Bracci R. Evoking of absent motor components in CNS lesions. Pisa, Editori Giardini. 1986;88.
- [2] Longo D, Longo L, Lippi P, Cherubini G, Mangé V. Effects of laser therapy and Grimaldi's muscle shortening manoeuvre on motor control of subjects with incomplete spinal cord injuries. *Laser Therapy*. 2017;26(3):203-9.
- [3] Longo D, Santini G, Cherubini G, Melchiorre D, Ferrarello F, Bagni MA. The muscle shortening maneuver in individuals with stroke: a consideration-of-concept randomized pilot trial. *Topics in Stroke Rehabilitation*. 2023 Nov 17;30(8):807-19.
- [4] Longo D, Ammannati L, Melchiorre D, Serafini I, Bagni MA, Ferrarello F. The Muscle Shortening Maneuver: a noninvasive approach to the treatment of peroneal nerve injury. A case report. *Physiotherapy theory and practice*. 2024 Jan 2;40(1):176-83.
- [5] <https://www.kinovea.org>.
- [6] <https://exrx.net/Kinesiology/Segments>.
- [7] Moura, Jairo Terra, Hakan Elmali, and Nejat Olgac. "Sliding mode control with sliding perturbation observer." (1997): 657-665

Fig. 1. Developed system with subject and test bed.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the implemented control algorithm.

Fig. 3. Trajectory tracking results from 140 to 150 seconds (amplitude 4 cm, and frequency 1 Hz).